

ISSUES OF CONSIDERATION OF CHILDREN'S TEMPERAMENTS IN
THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

Educator-pedagogue of creative school named after I. Yusupov
Aymuratova Arukhan Yusupovna

ABSTRACT

This article provides detailed information about the temperament, its features, characteristics, types and the scope of the education that is needed in the process of educating young people and having psychological contact with them. Education and training does not change the temperament, but it corrects the shortcomings of the temperament, changes its desirable qualities and achieves the goal of correcting the valuable characteristics of the individual based on this temperament and this article discusses a number of these issues, solutions are provided.

Keywords: temperament, nervous system, psychological process, melancholic, sanguine, phlegmatic, choleric types, behavior, activity and talent.

Introduction. As a result of the reforms implemented in the education system in our country, hardworking, selfless, loyal and active personnel are being trained in the education system at that time. The sharp changes in the development of society in modern times bring qualitatively new and relatively favorable changes. Here, the level of development of the human intellect, the regulator of its mental capabilities, and its moral requirements pay attention to itself. Currently, each chapter focuses on the science of psychology itself. Self-awareness, self-awareness, the change of a person's character, temperament develops from his childhood. In the science of psychology, it is possible to see that temperament is fully expressed by the psychological characteristics of a person. Temperament,

based on psychological therapy, is an individual characteristic that reflects the emotions of a person in front of his eyes and in his own behavior. Each person has different speed, strength and correctness of emotions. They move quickly, strongly and correctly. In some girls, such movements are low, slow and do not last long. The specific characteristics of temperament are associated with emotions that can change a person's impact on the environment.

The signs of different temperaments are visible from childhood. The spiritual world of a person is a complex of various movements, one of which appears only when it is planted, and it rules like a continuous chain system. In the soul of a person with the right reason, there are thoughts about the past, thoughts about the past, thoughts about the future, successful intentions, wishes, goals and wishes, thoughts, mental exercises, emotional well-being, and patience. Instead of changing places, your ontogenetic world is characterized by me. Psychic world, its aspect, content, form, scope, variation, characteristics, quality, mechanism, and in a human being, in a different way, in a different way. Finally, it is necessary for people to learn to respond to natural phenomena, social realities, influencing factors quickly or with some kind of training.

In psychology, there is a certain degree of separation between individual dynamic differences related to temperament. In the field of psychology, temperament characteristics are defined as a complex of stable, variable individual typological characteristics of the psyche, which determine the dynamics of mental activity of a person. These distinctions build a structure that develops a comparative temperament in motives, mental states, goals, and services, which have different form and content. During the socio-historical development of the field of psychology, the opinions expressed in comparison with temperament, the studies on its materiality have been various, and have served to explain the

psychological characteristics of the individual in different ways. Temperament is derived from the Latin word "temperamentum", which means "temperament"¹.

According to Hippocrates, there are four types of fluids (hilt) in the human body, which can be eaten by horses (Greek "chole"), blood (Latin sanguis yaki sanguinis), fat (Greek melas "black", "chole""horse") it was like that. Tell him: The quality of the horse is dryness, and its function is to keep the body dry. The change of the blood is heat, and its function is to keep the body warm. The fat man's behavior became a problem, and his duty was to keep the problem. According to the teaching of Hippocrates, each of them contains four liquid liquids, which means that they stand on top of each other. It was said that some of the temperaments (Latin temperamentum) are strong, but the right people lose their temperament, for example, it is said that choleric has a yellow horse, sanguine has blood, and melancholic has a fat head. At present, information about the genetics of the nervous system growth type (genotype) is very much obtained as a result of comparative animal studies. If the typology of temperament is compared according to people's temperaments, it can be seen that there are groups of people with slightly similar characteristics.

In this article, the collection (complex) of distinctions, collected materials about temperament types, was explained. Temperament type in modern times does not mean a special complex of characteristics that are dominant for certain groups of people, but a systematic, necessary interrelationship of these characteristics. It is possible to say that the distinctions characterizing the temperament type are interrelated in a systematic way. People with different temperament types have different character traits and personality traits. Important characteristics of temperament types are listed below.

¹ A.K.Shamshetova, R.N.Melibayeva, K.E.Usmanova, I.O.Khaydarov. General psychology. 0 tutorial. - T.: "Barkamol fayz media", 2018. - 272 p.

Sanguine is hyperreactivity process. Children laugh loudly even at things that are not there. A fact that is not necessary will cause severe pain. He responds to all the things that attract his attention with a quick and energetic response. Signs and movements are clearly visible in the mirror. Looking at his face, it is not difficult to know how he is and how he relates to things and people. Pay attention quickly, it has low sensitivity. Activity and reactivity are equal. Call him to discipline quickly. His movements are fast, his speech is fast, he gets into the conversation very quickly, and he quickly gathers attention. His mind is quick, resourceful, slow down the movements. Feelings, moods, excitement, and expectations have changed a lot. The new people are getting into me quickly. Adaptation to new demands and circumstances is learned. Scientific experiments are quickly created and quickly modified. I'm smart, extroverted.

Choleric type has low sensitivity with sanguine blood, high reactivity is also separated from activity, but reactivity prevails over activity. Mental pace is fast. If he starts one of them, he will be very jet-lagged, but only if the other one is hot. **Phlegmatic**-sensitivity is low, sensitivity is low, it is difficult to laugh, express anger, and spoil mood. **Melancholy**-high sensitivity is characteristic. It is not stable, the mental temp is low. Rigid (stiff), introvert is a change. A person's temperament determines the individual way of working. For the same reason, the individual method of work means the individual system of goals achieved by a person on his own. A separate set of temperament characteristics is reflected in the individual process of human behavior in the process of knowing the relations of human behavior. The individual way of working is related not only to temperament, but also to other reasons, which appear in the process of experience².

²A.K.Shamshetova, R.N.Melibayeva, K.E.Usmanova, I.O.Khaydarov. General psychology tutorial. - T.: "Barkamol faiz media", 2018. - 272 p

In conclusion that human temperament is related to education, upbringing process, social world, and scientific experiences of all people. He found that the behavior of successful people in marriage was also related to the temperament of the body.

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